

The PoDIUM project and the role of communications as a CCAM enabler

Marcel Kern, Markus Wimmer
Nokia Solutions and Networks GmbH & Co. KG
Ulm, Germany

Lazaros Gkatzikis, Vasilis Sourlas
Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICCS)
Athens, Greece

Michael Buchholz, Alexander Scheible
Institute of Measurement, Control and Microtechnology
Ulm University, Germany

Amr Rizk
University of Duisburg-Essen
Duisburg, Germany

Tobias Müller
Robert Bosch GmbH
Ulm Germany

Abstract—Advanced Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), including reliable communications, is a key component of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM). This paper summarizes the vision of the EU Horizon PoDIUM project to enable CCAM in real traffic conditions. The generic PDI architecture derived within the project is presented, which covers a diverse set of uses cases and can be seen as a blueprint for the PDI of the future. We provide a detailed overview of the alternative communication types and technologies that are considered in the project. Finally, we focus on five cutting-edge PDI-assisted CCAM use cases that will be realized and demonstrated in real road traffic. These uses cases combine i) multi-connectivity communication, ii) a distributed and interoperable data management and IT environment including the cloud, edge, and local levels, and iii) cooperative services for intelligent transportation systems like digital twins or cooperative traffic management, taking non-connected vehicles as well as vulnerable road users into account.

Keywords—Automated Mobility, Connectivity and communication technologies

I. INTRODUCTION

Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) is not only seen as a key to achieving the EU's Vision Zero [1], but also to enhance the availability of mobility services for everyone. The implementation of such Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) for road traffic, especially for cooperative behavior, relies on seamless communication among the road users themselves (vehicle-to-vehicle, V2V) as well as between each of them and the infrastructure part of the system (vehicle-to-infrastructure, V2I), jointly named vehicle-to-anything (V2X) communication. Overall, such a CCAM ITS requires advanced Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI), where the physical part comprises of classical road infrastructure like traffic signs or traffic lights as well as, e.g., communication networks and computation capabilities, not forgetting the vehicles themselves. Examples for the digital part are digital maps together with digitally

processable descriptions of the traffic rules as well as the data collected, processed, and communicated by the road users and the infrastructure.

The PoDIUM project [2], which is funded by the EU within its Horizon Europe program, addresses the need of such PDI enhancements by developing and realizing five CCAM use cases (UCs) in three living labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy and Spain, including urban and highway traffic as well as cross-border driving. These UCs strive to showcase the capabilities of such an ITS that advances the state of the art by providing

- multi-connectivity to optimally utilize the available communication channels, for enhanced reliability and reduced latency;
- a distributed environment for data storage between the local computing entities, the edge and the cloud levels;
- an IT environment allowing for a flexible service deployment between these three levels;
- methods to ensure software integrity and assess data trustworthiness; and
- relevant services for CCAM integrating also non-connected vehicles and vulnerable road users (VRUs).

These technical innovations aim towards an increased safety of road traffic in general and especially for VRUs. PoDIUM aims also at increasing the traffic efficiency and, thus, reducing the carbon footprint of road traffic. PoDIUM will pursue tangible impact to the respective domains by providing input to respective standardization bodies from real-world experience with such a CCAM system, and developing new business models and market services in the field of ITS.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section II, we present the generic PoDIUM PDI architecture that can accommodate all the PoDIUM UCs and services. In Section III, we elaborate on specific communication aspects that have been considered in the project, as communications have been identified as a critical component of the PoDIUM vision. In Section IV, we describe the 5 advanced CCAM UCs that will illustrate, validate and evaluate

the PoDIUM enhancements through deployment in real-life traffic conditions. Finally, a conclusion summarizes the paper findings and future plans.

PoDIUM will provide on a technical level across all LLs and UCs.

The road is equipped with: RSUs, sensors connected to the system through Sensor Processing Unit SPUs or directly, and

Fig. 1. High-level overview of the PoDIUM architecture

II. THE PoDIUM PDI ARCHITECTURE

The PoDIUM consortium has developed a generic PDI architecture that, on the one hand, builds on previous connected infrastructure architectures, like [13] and [14], thus is backward compatible for the respective use cases realized with those architectures. On the other hand, the PoDIUM architecture allows the realization of the new CCAM UCs, ensuring interoperability between the different LLs. A bottom-up approach to derive the architecture was chosen, by first deriving the following sub-views of the overall architecture:

- Communication view,
- Functional view,
- Data flow and storage view,
- Information Technology (IT) environment view,
- Software integrity and data truthfulness view.

Each of the views, described in detail in [10], allows respective experts to easily understand the design and needs of this architecture for their field and to derive an implementation for a specific use case. Due to the common architecture, the implementations remain interoperable, e.g. with respect to data interfaces using C-ITS messages.

From the detailed views, an overall high-level view, as shown in Fig. 1, was derived to highlight the main contributions that

connected Traffic Lights (TLs) (omitted from figure for simplicity, but similar to SPU). All types of road users are considered and supported, namely legacy (non-connected) vehicles and other non-connected road users; connected VRUs with a cellular User Equipment (UE); Connected conventional Vehicles (CV), connected Emergency Vehicles (EV) and Connected Automated Vehicles (CAV) with an On-Board Unit (OBU).

The platform services are either hosted on a MEC server or on the central cloud, determined mainly by their latency requirements. The basic communication technologies of PoDIUM are described in Section III.

To ensure the integrity of the software and exchanged CCAM data, a trusted computing approach is developed on Trusted Platform Modules (TPMs). Many services depend on the DT, which fuses incoming information from different sources (e.g. C-ITS messages and infrastructure sensor data) into an enhanced environmental model. Thus, the reliability of the DT data and, in consequence, of its sources is crucial. To reinforce this aspect, the PoDIUM architecture includes trust building and data truthfulness evaluation of data sources.

III. COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGIES IN PoDIUM

Communication technologies available for CCAM can be characterized in terms of communication range, reliability, latency, capacity, and costs. A basic classification is on cellular and ad-hoc ones.

Cellular network communication, also called mobile network communication [3], provide extended coverage through the deployed network infrastructure and can be further classified into:

- LTE and 5G cm-Wave is wireless communication in frequency bands between 450 MHz and 6 GHz, which support a channel bandwidth between 5 MHz and 100 MHz. cm-Wave typically provides wide area coverage and can offer low latency and high throughput rates.
- 5G mm-Wave is defined for frequency bands between 24.25 GHz and 52.60 GHz, which support a channel bandwidth between 50 MHz and 400 MHz. 5G mm-Wave provides restricted (local) coverage but can combine very high throughput rates with very low latency. A seamless communication (handover) between 5G mm-Wave and 5G cm-Wave is supported, i.e. the user connection at a lower data rate can be maintained when leaving the hot spot.

Ad-hoc wireless network communication enables end-user devices to communicate without relying on cellular network infrastructure, wireless access points or any other traditional network infrastructure equipment.

- ITS-G5, or IEEE 802.11p is an amendment to the IEEE 802.11 WLAN standard to add wireless access in vehicular environments, for a vehicular communication system. It defines enhancements to 802.11 required to support Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) applications [4]. ITS-G5 provides restricted (local) coverage with moderate to low throughput rates combined with very low latency.
- Sidelink (SL, PC5) refers to direct communication between UEs without the data going through the network, based on the 3GPP standards LTE and 5G (e.g. [5], [6], [7]). The SL (PC5) interface does not necessarily require assistance from a mobile network and provides restricted (local) coverage with moderate to low throughput rates combined with very low latency.

An additional special category of communications considered in PoDIUM is the 60 GHz WLAN, or IEEE 802.11ad. This is an amendment to the IEEE 802.11 Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) standard [4] that has not been extensively considered and evaluated for CCAM applications. 60 GHz WLAN provides restricted (local) coverage through the installation of dedicated wireless access point but can combine very high throughput rates with very low latency.

The communication ranges and throughput rates of the above-mentioned technologies are outlined in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Coverage-Throughput relationship of communication technologies

An important performance criterion of communications is the Quality of Service (QoS). It is the ability of a communication system to dynamically allocate a set of communication characteristics to a user of a group of users, such as guaranteed throughput rates, maximum throughput rates, minimum reliability, maximum and/or average latency, etc. For instance, in cellular networks, QoS can be realized with subscriber prioritization, and especially in 5G with network slices for dedicated user including vehicular user. 3GPP REL 17, several 5G QoS Indicators (5QI) for V2X were specified, each offering delay-critical guaranteed bit rate (GBR) with specific QoS characteristics (from [8], Table 5.7.4-1):

TABLE I. 5G V2X QoS INDICATORS

5QI	Packet Delay Budget	Packet Error Rate	Default max. data burst vol.
83	30ms	10^{-4}	1354 bytes
84	5ms	10^{-5}	1354 bytes
85	5ms	10^{-5}	255 bytes
86	5ms	10^{-4}	1354 bytes

Indicative uses of those quality levels are:

- QCI 83: UE-RSU Platooning, advanced driving, cooperative lane changes with low Level of Automation (LoA)
- QCI 84: Intelligent Transport Systems
- QCI 85: remote driving
- QCI 86: advanced driving, collision avoidance, platooning with high LoA

Next to using a single technology for the communication between two endpoints, PoDIUM further deploys and studies the Multi-Connectivity and Hybrid Communication types.

A. Hybrid Communications

In hybrid communications, all messages are simultaneously transmitted using all available communication technologies. Messages and data packets are always duplicated so that they can be transmitted on every available communication interface. High

redundancy is realized with no regards to the criticality of individual messages and data packets. [10]

Hybrid communication is implemented through routing functions in all entities using this functionality. One example of a PoDIUM use case implementation is in a CAV, in which the C-ITS message handling is based on hybrid communication unit with one PC5 modem and one LTE modem. All C-ITS messages are duplicated in the AMQP client. Then one message is forwarded to the PC5 modem and the duplicated message to the LTE modem. The receiving end is responsible for the deduplication if the message is successfully received twice.

B. Multi-Connectivity

Multi-connectivity is the ability of communication devices to intelligently schedule messages and data packets over the different available communication technologies.

A scheduler is deployed on the CV/CAV through a transparent communication PC that is connected to the CAV processing and computing server. The communication PC is connected via 5G modem, 60-GHz-Wifi transceivers and an ITS-G5 OBU and it forwards all messages (e.g. CAM, CPM and MCM) obtained from the computing server on a selected subset of the available communication technologies. On the MEC, RSU, and SPU, the scheduler program runs directly on the server (optionally using a similarly transparent communication PC) with the same aforementioned capability. The scheduler configuration through match/action tables allows to configure the mapping of specific messages or message types to communication technologies/interfaces [9].

Multi-connectivity aims to choose the best available transmission technology or technologies among those available during the time of data transmission to enhance transmission reliability, availability and redundancy of the PDI system, and potentially improve latency.

The criteria according to which an interface is selected to be used are configured in the scheduler and can be dynamically updated. A programmable scheduler (P4 [16]) controls where each packet goes according to the following principles:

- an API for external configuration enables network apps, i.e., external programs, to configure the functions of the scheduler
- a local control plane dictates the data plane on how to use its available connections, through
 - internal default parameters; or
 - external configuration obtained from the configuration API
- a data plane function is responsible for the actual data transfer

C. The PoDIUM communication view

All those aspects are captured in the PoDIUM project and can be summarized as shown in Figure 3. This communication view serves as an abstract representation of the PoDIUM communication architecture covering the diverse requirements of various LLs and UCs. This standards-compliant overarching

platform fosters efficient communication, data exchange, and collaboration between different entities within each of the UCs presented next.

Fig. 3. High-level communication view of the PoDIUM system

IV. PoDIUM use cases

Based on the UCs goals, the PoDIUM consortium has derived requirements on the involved components, especially the PDI and the connected road users, as well as on the overall system ([11], [15]). Examples are the availability of specific mobile communication channels, computing devices on road, edge or cloud level, or latencies and bandwidth requirements. This section summarizes the UCs that have generated the CCAM requirements and have consequently influenced the development of the PoDIUM PDI architecture.

The German LL hosts one UC, whereas both the Spanish and the Italian LL realize two UCs each. In the following, a short summary of each UC is given, sorted by the respective LLs. A more detailed description of the UCs can be found in [11].

A. UC in the German living lab

The German LL implements the UC1 “Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm”. A pilot installation with infrastructure sensors as well as a mobile test network exist from previous projects ([12], [13], [14]) in a suburban area, covering respective urban roads with one lane per direction, including an unsignalized T-junction. The test mobile network operated by Nokia features a mobile edge computing (MEC) server, to which the infrastructure sensors and the connected road users are connected and a Digital Twin (DT) of the current traffic is generated. In PoDIUM, based on this DT, a cooperative planer will cooperatively manage the traffic on one of the roads where one lane is blocked, e.g. by a parking truck or a construction side, so that both directions have to share the single remaining lane. In the first scenario, this cooperation will be realized with two Connected Automated Vehicles (CAVs), whereas the second scenario includes a connected VRU, a bicyclist, instead of one of the CAVs. From a technical perspective, this UC explores the feasibility of realizing the first scenario without the infrastructure sensors, i.e., only based on the environment information transmitted from the connected road users, including the assessment of the data reliability within the DT generation. It will evaluate the exploitation of multi-connectivity, i.e., the use of

redundantly available mobile communication channels, which will include a cellular 5G network with cm-Wave and mm-Wave bands and two ad-hoc networks, namely ITS-G5 and a 60-GHz WiFi network. The second scenario focuses on PDI-assisted operation for integrating VRUs.

B. UCs in the Spanish living lab

The Spanish LL features two different UCs. UC2 “PDI for User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs” will be realized in the City of Barcelona and comprises of three scenarios that will be evaluated simultaneously: An emergency vehicle (EV), e.g., a firefighters’ truck, shares its route and continuously its position with a Traffic Management System (TMS), which allows the TMS to prioritize this vehicle at signalized intersections. Furthermore, the infrastructure will warn the other connected vehicles (CVs) on the route about the approaching EV. Additionally, potential risk situations for VRUs detected by the infrastructure in the event of an approaching EV will trigger the infrastructure to send a respective warning to the affected VRU as well as to CVs. Finally, based on the collected information, improved general traffic management strategies will be applied for all CVs. All connected entities will share the relevant data (location, speed, destination, and origin) with the TMS, which in turn will provide the current traffic status as well as route options based on optimal traffic control strategies and route optimization algorithms.

In contrast to the inner-city focus of UC2, UC3 “Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor” will be implemented on a segment of the Figueres-Perpignan corridor across the French-Spanish border. For different sections of the route, the current traffic status will be retrieved from a combination of infrastructure sensors and V2I communication. Traffic management strategies will allow for safe operation, which will include tele-operation via 5G of automated vehicles. From a traffic point of view, the scenarios will involve daily commuting via a shuttle as well as addressing safety incidents across the border.

C. UCs in the Italian living lab

The Italian LL also hosts two UCs, one with focus on urban traffic and one with a highway focus. UC4 “Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance”, similarly to UCs 1 and 2, focuses on urban traffic. A DT of an urban crossroad will be generated from all the available sources, i.e., connected road users, infrastructure sensors perceiving information on non-connected road users, and other sources like traffic signal phases, leveraging the cooperative awareness for all connected road users. This DT allows the application of a VRU-aware suggestion of motion for the oncoming vehicles. A special focus of this UC is laid on trust when generating the DT. Thus, mechanisms like Trusting Platform Modules (TPMs) to ensure software integrity will be implemented.

UC5 “Use Case 5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel” includes a DT of the traffic in a highway tunnel. This UCs

addresses the two main challenges when driving in a tunnel, namely road safety and vehicle localization despite the lack of open-sky GNSS information. For the latter, two approaches will be investigated: artificial GNSS signals provided by the tunnel infrastructure as well as trilateration from V2X signal sources. These will allow for a precise DT, which is used as the basis to assess the risk of the current traffic situation. Eventually, the connected road users will be warned by the infrastructure of a potential risky situation.

CONCLUSIONS

CCAM has great potential to improve traffic efficiency and road safety and is expected to play an essential role in meeting global climate goals for the mobility sector despite the continuously increasing traffic. The integration of CCAM into modern transportation systems relies heavily on the advancement of both physical and digital infrastructures, coupled with reliable communication technologies. This paper presented a CCAM architecture blueprint based on enhanced PDI. Derived from the requirements of real-world UCs within the PoDIUM project, this architecture extends the existing architectures, including multi-connectivity and hybrid data storage, integrating also connected and non-connected VRUs into the system. Furthermore, the key technical developments to realize this architecture have been presented. As a next step, the PoDIUM consortium will implement the systems and components within three LLs in Europe to demonstrate its powerfulness, evaluating the UCs in real-world traffic by the end of 2025.

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